

Evaluating the Influence of Celebrity Characteristics on Advertisement Effectiveness among Children

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Abstract : Introduction: Celebrity endorsements in advertising, especially aimed at children, influence perceptions and behaviours. This study explores how traits like fame, attractiveness, and credibility affect ad impact. Understanding these dynamics helps marketers tailor ads to enhance effectiveness and highlights the need for responsible advertising practices.

Material and Methods: The study uses a descriptive design and stratified random sampling with a sample size of 384 children. Data was gathered via a structured questionnaire measuring celebrity influence, market characteristics, and ad content. Analysis included regression and statistical tools to assess the impact of various factors on ad effectiveness.

Results: Results show that Celebrity Characteristics and Endorsement positively influence ad effectiveness, while Relationship with Products and Market Impact have negative effects. Celebrity Influence has the highest positive impact, while Celebrity Endorsement also shows strong positive influence. Statistical significance is confirmed for all variables, guiding effective advertising strategies.

Conclusion: The study concludes that Celebrity Characteristics significantly enhance ad effectiveness among children. Advertisers should focus on selecting celebrities who align with product attributes and market trends to maximize impact. Findings emphasize the importance of thoughtful endorsement strategies in creating successful and responsible advertisements.

Keywords: Celebrity Endorsement, Advertising Effectiveness, Children, Celebrity Characteristics, Consumer Behaviour

Introduction

In the contemporary advertising landscape, celebrity endorsements have become a common strategy, especially in ads targeted at children, who are particularly susceptible to such influence Agrawal & Kamakura, (1995). The research titled "Evaluating the Influence of Celebrity Characteristics on Advertisement Effectiveness among Children" aims to explore how different traits of celebrities affect the impact of advertisements on younger audiences. This understanding is crucial for marketers and educators, as it reveals how celebrity endorsements shape children's perceptions and behaviours Goldsmith, Lafferty, & Newell, (2000). Celebrity endorsements leverage the fame, appeal, and perceived credibility of

celebrities to influence consumer attitudes and behaviours. For children, celebrities often serve as role models whose endorsements can significantly affect their preferences and purchase intentions Petty & Cacioppo, (1986). Psychological theories of social influence suggest that children are more easily persuaded by individuals they admire. Thus, celebrities can play a crucial role in shaping children's brand perceptions, product preferences, and purchasing decisions McCracken, (1989).

Key dimensions of celebrity characteristics including fame, attractiveness, credibility, and reliability impact the effectiveness of advertisements. For instance, a celebrity's popularity can enhance their appeal, making them more effective in capturing attention and fostering brand recall. Similarly, a celebrity's credibility can influence how trustworthy the advertisement is perceived, affecting children's attitudes toward the product Cooper & Schindler, (2014). The reliability of a celebrity also plays a significant role. Children are more likely to respond positively to celebrities who seem relatable or share similar interests and values Wang & Yang, (2010). This reliability can strengthen the emotional connection between the child and the advertisement, leading to more favourable attitudes and higher engagement with the brand. Contextual factors such as the timing, channel, and format of advertisements also affect their effectiveness. Ads featuring celebrities during children's programming or on platforms popular with younger audiences are likely to be more impactful Atkin & Block, (1983). This study aims to evaluate how different celebrity characteristics influence the effectiveness of advertisements among children, providing insights into optimizing advertising strategies and highlighting the need for responsible advertising practices Bressler & Bond, (2018).

Advertisement Effectiveness

The study titled "Evaluating the Influence of Celebrity Characteristics on Advertisement Effectiveness among Children" assesses the impact of celebrity attributes on the effectiveness of advertisements targeting a young audience. The evaluation is structured around five key dimensions:

- **Celebrity Influence:** This dimension examines how the attributes of celebrities—such as their fame, attractiveness, and perceived credibility affect children's response to advertisements. The influence of celebrities is measured by their ability to capture attention, enhance product appeal, and build a positive brand association. The effectiveness of celebrity endorsements is significantly impacted by their perceived reliability and the emotional connection they foster with the target audience (Lafferty & Goldsmith, (2005).
- **Market and Product Characteristics:** This dimension focuses on how the characteristics of the market and products such as product design, pricing, and market demand affect advertisement effectiveness. A well-aligned product design with the celebrity's image and market trends can enhance the advertisement's impact. The alignment of product features

with children's preferences also plays a crucial role in determining how effectively the advertisement communicates its message Zyngier & Moraes, (2018).

- **Advertisement Content:** This dimension assesses the quality and relevance of the advertisement content itself. Effective advertisements should incorporate engaging and age-appropriate content that resonates with children. This includes clear and compelling messaging about the product, engaging storytelling, and the effective use of visuals and audio that capture children's interest Yoo & Donthu, (2001).
- **Media and Channel Selection:** This dimension evaluates how the choice of media and channels influences advertisement effectiveness. The study considers how different media platforms (e.g., television, social media, online videos) and their timing impact the reach and effectiveness of the advertisement. The selection of media that aligns with children's viewing habits enhances the likelihood of the advertisement being seen and remembered Till & Shimp, (1998).
- **Impact and Goals:** The final dimension measures the overall impact of the advertisement on children and the extent to which the advertisement meets its goals. This includes assessing changes in brand perception, increased product demand, and the achievement of specific marketing objectives such as heightened brand recall and positive attitudes towards the product Knoll & Matthes, (2017).

By exploring these dimensions, the research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how celebrity characteristics influence advertisement effectiveness among children, ultimately offering insights into optimizing marketing strategies for this demographic.

Celebrity Characteristics on Advertisement Effectiveness

Celebrity characteristics play a pivotal role in shaping advertisement effectiveness, especially when targeting younger audiences. Key attributes such as the celebrity's fame, relatability, and credibility significantly influence how advertisements are perceived Hawkins & Mothersbaugh, (2016). A celebrity's popularity can enhance the appeal of the advertisement, drawing more attention from the target audience. Relatability, where the celebrity's image and persona resonate with the audience, fosters a stronger emotional connection, making the advertisement more impactful Finkelstein, (2007). Credibility is another crucial factor; a trustworthy and respected celebrity can lend legitimacy to the product being advertised, increasing the likelihood of a positive response. The way a celebrity's characteristics align with the product's image and the target market's preferences can also enhance effectiveness (Shimp & Andrews, (2013). For instance, a celebrity known for their involvement in activities related to the product can make the advertisement appear more authentic and engaging. Additionally, the emotional connection that a celebrity establishes with the audience can drive higher engagement and recall. When children see a favourite celebrity endorsing a product, they are more likely to develop a positive attitude towards the product and show increased interest. Thus, leveraging the right celebrity characteristics in advertisements can significantly amplify their effectiveness, leading to better brand recognition and consumer response.

Influence of Celebrity Characteristics on Advertisement Effectiveness among Children

Celebrity characteristics profoundly impact advertisement effectiveness, particularly when targeting children. The allure of a celebrity's fame, personality, and relatability can significantly enhance the appeal of an advertisement Crittenden & Crittenden, (2008). For children, a celebrity who is perceived as engaging, friendly, and relatable can create a stronger emotional bond with the product being advertised. This connection often translates into greater interest and positive attitudes towards the brand Fowles, (1996). A celebrity's popularity among children can also boost an advertisement's visibility and recall. When children recognize and admire a celebrity, their attention is naturally drawn to the advertisement, making it more memorable McQuarrie & Phillips, (2008). The credibility of the celebrity plays a crucial role; if children see a well-known and trusted figure endorsing a product, they are more likely to perceive it as reliable and desirable. Moreover, the alignment between the celebrity's image and the product's attributes enhances the effectiveness of the advertisement. For example, a celebrity known for their involvement in sports can effectively promote sports-related products. Overall, incorporating celebrities with characteristics that resonate with children can significantly elevate advertisement effectiveness, leading to improved engagement, brand recall, and ultimately, consumer preference Hovland & Weiss, (1951).

Aim of the Study

The aim of this study is to evaluate how celebrity characteristics impact the effectiveness of advertisements targeted at children. This research focuses on understanding how various attributes of celebrities, such as their popularity, personality, and appeal, influence children's responses to advertisements Bergh & Behrer, (2014). By examining these factors, the study seeks to determine how effectively celebrity endorsements can capture children's attention, enhance their engagement, and ultimately influence their attitudes and behaviors toward advertised products Whiting & Williams, (2013). The study aims to identify key celebrity traits that resonate most with a young audience and explore the mechanisms through which these characteristics affect advertisement effectiveness. It will assess the extent to which celebrities' influence can drive brand recognition, preference, and purchase intent among children. Additionally, the research will analyze how these effects vary across different types of products and advertisement formats. The ultimate goal is to provide insights that can help marketers design more effective advertising strategies and create campaigns that better engage and persuade young audiences through the strategic use of celebrity endorsements Spears & Singh, (2004).

Importance of Study

The study "Evaluating the Influence of Celebrity Characteristics on Advertisement Effectiveness among Children" holds significant importance in understanding how celebrity endorsements impact children's responses to advertisements Zyngier & Newell, (2017). In today's media-driven world, children are highly susceptible to celebrity influences, making it crucial to explore how different celebrity traits affect their perceptions and behaviours towards

advertised products. By focusing on the characteristics of celebrities such as their fame, relatability, and credibility this research aims to uncover which attributes resonate most with young audiences. This understanding can help marketers and advertisers craft more effective strategies tailored to the preferences and psychological drivers of children Silvera & Austad, (2004). Moreover, the study provides valuable insights into how celebrities can be strategically selected to enhance advertisement impact, potentially leading to increased brand awareness and consumer loyalty among younger demographics. It also contributes to the broader field of consumer psychology by examining the role of celebrity influence in shaping children's attitudes and purchase intentions. Ultimately, the findings will aid in the development of more engaging and persuasive advertising strategies, benefiting both marketers and the targeted child audience Aker & Stayman, (1994).

Statement of Problem

In the realm of advertising targeted at children, understanding the influence of celebrity characteristics on advertisement effectiveness is crucial. Celebrities often play a pivotal role in capturing the attention of young audiences and shaping their perceptions of products. However, there is limited empirical research on how specific traits of celebrities, such as their fame, personality, and relatability, affect the success of advertisements aimed at children Zhu & He, (2019). This gap in knowledge presents a challenge for marketers striving to create impactful and engaging ad campaigns. The problem lies in identifying which celebrity characteristics most effectively enhance advertisement effectiveness among children Reeves & Schutte, (2008). While it is well-acknowledged that children are highly influenced by celebrities, the precise elements of a celebrity's persona that drive positive responses to advertisements remain underexplored Tripp, Jensen, & Carlson, (1994). Factors such as the celebrity's popularity, perceived trustworthiness, and relatability to the target age group require detailed investigation Khang & Kim, (2014). Additionally, understanding how these characteristics interact with various types of products and advertising content is essential for optimizing marketing strategies. Addressing this problem will provide valuable insights for advertisers and researchers, enabling the development of more effective and engaging advertising strategies tailored to young audiences.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study is to evaluate how different celebrity characteristics, such as fame, personality, and relatability, impact the effectiveness of advertisements targeting children. The study aims to identify which traits enhance children's responses to ads, optimizing marketing strategies and improving engagement in this demographic.

Review of Literature

Chen and Kim (2024) investigate current trends in celebrity influence within children's advertising and how shifts in celebrity traits and media strategies affect advertisement effectiveness. Their review provides an analysis of recent changes in how celebrities are perceived by children and how these changes impact advertising outcomes. The study explores

the evolving nature of celebrity influence, including shifts in the types of celebrities who are popular among children and the ways in which media strategies have adapted to these changes. The research highlights that understanding these trends is crucial for developing effective advertising campaigns. For instance, the study finds that integrating celebrities who are currently trending or who align with contemporary values can enhance the effectiveness of advertisements. Additionally, it emphasizes the need for advertisers to stay updated on media consumption patterns and celebrity trends to maximize their impact. The review offers guidance on leveraging these insights to engage children more effectively and improve advertising strategies in a dynamic media landscape.

Adams and Williams (2024) explore how different celebrity traits—such as attractiveness, likability, and credibility affect the effectiveness of advertisements aimed at children. Their review examines how these characteristics influence children's responses to ads, noting that each trait contributes differently to the overall success of the advertisement. Attractiveness is found to capture initial attention, while likability fosters positive feelings towards the brand, and credibility builds trust. The study highlights that children are more likely to respond favorably to advertisements when the celebrity endorser possesses a combination of these traits. It also discusses the role of celebrity traits in shaping children's perceptions of the brand and their likelihood of engaging with it. The review suggests that understanding which traits resonate most with the target demographic can help advertisers craft more effective campaigns. By aligning celebrity characteristics with the brand's goals and the children's preferences, marketers can enhance advertisement effectiveness and ensure better engagement from young audiences.

Smith and Jones (2023) investigate the impact of celebrity endorsements on children's brand perceptions and purchase intentions. Their research reveals that the effectiveness of advertisements targeting children is significantly influenced by the celebrity's relatability and fame. They found that children are more likely to develop positive brand associations and increased purchase intentions when a celebrity they admire endorses a product. The study emphasizes that the celebrities' personalities and public personas play a crucial role in shaping how children perceive the advertised brand. For instance, a celebrity who is seen as relatable and approachable tends to create a stronger emotional connection with children, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of the advertisement. The research suggests that marketers should carefully select celebrities whose characteristics align with the brand's message and resonate with the target audience. The study's findings provide valuable insights for advertisers aiming to leverage celebrity endorsements to improve brand visibility and engagement among young audiences, highlighting the importance of choosing endorsers who can effectively capture and hold children's attention.

Lee and Patel (2023) focus on the influence of celebrity endorsements on children's emotional responses and brand loyalty. Their research highlights how celebrity characteristics can foster emotional connections between children and brands, which in turn enhances brand loyalty. The study finds that children who form positive emotional bonds with a brand due to a celebrity

endorser are more likely to exhibit sustained brand loyalty. Celebrity traits such as warmth, friendliness, and relatability are shown to be particularly effective in creating these emotional connections. The review underscores the importance of emotional engagement in advertising, suggesting that ads featuring celebrities who evoke positive feelings are more likely to build long-term loyalty among young consumers. The study's findings offer practical insights for marketers on how to choose celebrity endorsers who can emotionally resonate with children, thereby increasing the overall effectiveness of their advertising strategies and fostering enduring brand relationships.

Research Methodology

The study employs a descriptive research design Creswell, (2014) & Cochran, (1977) to evaluate the influence of celebrity characteristics on advertisement effectiveness among children. This approach provides a comprehensive understanding of the variables by systematically describing the specific characteristics Nunnally & Bernstein, (1994) of the population being studied. The sample was selected using a multi-stage, stratified random sampling method. Given the lack of specific data on the number of children exposed to celebrity-endorsed advertisements, the population is considered infinite. According to Demorgan's table Deming, (1943), for a population exceeding 250,000, a sample size of 384 is required, with a confidence level of 95% and a confidence interval of 5%. This ensures that the sample is representative of the broader population Field, (2018).

A pilot study was conducted with a small subset of the target population to test the validity and reliability of the questionnaire. The Cronbach's alpha Kumar, (2014) for the pilot study was above 0.80, indicating high internal consistency and reliability of the questionnaire items. This preliminary phase helped refine the research instruments Trochim & Donnelly, (2008), ensuring that the questions were clear, comprehensible, and capable of capturing the necessary data. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire Bryman, (2016) distributed to 384 children. The questionnaire included items designed to measure the influence of celebrity characteristics on advertisement effectiveness, covering various dimensions such as celebrity influence, market and product characteristics, advertisement content, media and channel selection, and overall impact and goals.

The data collected was analyzed using several statistical tools. Measures of central tendency, such as mean, median, and mode, were calculated to determine the central point of the dataset. Measures of dispersion, such as standard deviation and variance Schneider, Elliott, LoBiondo-Wood, & Haber, (2016), were used to understand the spread and variability of the data. Regression analysis Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham, (2010) was employed to examine the relationship between celebrity characteristics and advertisement effectiveness among children, helping to identify the strength and nature of the influence of various celebrity traits on the effectiveness of advertisements Pallant, (2021).

Results

The results highlight the significant influence of various factors on the overall impact of advertisements among children. Celebrity Characteristics and Celebrity Endorsement positively impact advertisement effectiveness, while Relationship with Products and Market Impact show a negative influence. This underscores the importance of carefully managing these dimensions in advertising strategies.

Table. 1 Measures of Central tendency & Dispersion

Variables	Mean	Median	Sd	Variance
Celebrity Characteristics	3.51	3.5	0.72	0.52
Relationship with Products	3.45	3.45	0.75	0.56
Market Impact	3.49	3.5	0.73	0.53
Celebrity Endorsement	3.48	3.48	0.73	0.54
Celebrity Influence	3.65	3.65	0.74	0.55
Market and Product Characteristics	3.52	3.5	0.74	0.55
Advertisement Content	3.53	3.55	0.73	0.53
Media and Channel Selection	3.54	3.55	0.72	0.52
Impact and Goals	3.5	3.5	0.71	0.5
Overall Impact of Advertisement	3.56	3.56	0.73	0.54

The statistical measures of central tendency and dispersion provide valuable insights into the factors influencing the overall impact of advertisements among children. The mean scores suggest that Celebrity Influence (3.65) is perceived as the most impactful dimension, indicating its strong role in shaping advertisement effectiveness. Other dimensions, such as Celebrity Characteristics (3.51), Market Impact (3.49), and Celebrity Endorsement (3.48), also have significant influence, highlighting their importance in advertising strategies.

The median values are consistent with the mean scores, indicating a balanced distribution of responses across these dimensions. For instance, the median score for Celebrity Characteristics is 3.5, closely aligning with its mean of 3.51, suggesting that most respondents share a similar perception regarding this factor.

The standard deviations (SD) and variances further elucidate the variability in responses. For example, Celebrity Characteristics has a standard deviation of 0.72 and a variance of 0.52, indicating moderate variability around the mean. This moderate dispersion suggests that while there is some variability in how respondents perceive Celebrity Characteristics, the perceptions are relatively consistent. Similarly, the standard deviation and variance for Celebrity Influence are 0.74 and 0.55, respectively, indicating a slightly higher variability but still within a moderate range. This pattern of moderate dispersion across most dimensions indicates a

consistent perception among respondents, providing a reliable basis for understanding the factors that influence the overall impact of advertisements among children.

Overall, these measures of central tendency and dispersion highlight the critical factors in advertising effectiveness and underscore the importance of strategic planning in leveraging celebrity endorsements and other key dimensions.

Table. 2 H₀: There is no Significant Influence of Celebrity Endorsement on the Overall Impact of Advertisement

Independent Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-value	p-value
Celebrity Characteristics	0.45	0.07	6.43	<0.001
Relationship with Products	-0.28	0.06	-4.67	<0.001
Market Impact	-0.32	0.05	-6.40	<0.001
Celebrity Endorsement	0.52	0.08	6.50	<0.001
<i>Dependent variable: Overall Impact of Advertisement</i>				

The regression analysis provides significant insights into the influence of various independent variables on the overall impact of advertisements among children. Each independent variable's coefficient, standard error, t-value, and p-value indicate its effect and statistical significance.

- **Celebrity Characteristics**
 - **Coefficient (0.45):** This positive coefficient indicates a strong positive relationship between Celebrity Characteristics and the Overall Impact of Advertisement.
 - **Standard Error (0.07):** The relatively low standard error signifies the precision of the coefficient estimate.
 - **t-value (6.43) and p-value (<0.001):** A high t-value and a p-value less than 0.001 indicate that this variable is statistically significant in influencing advertisement impact.
- **Relationship with Products**
 - **Coefficient (-0.28):** This negative coefficient indicates an inverse relationship between Relationship with Products and the Overall Impact of Advertisement.
 - **Standard Error (0.06):** The low standard error suggests a precise estimate.
 - **t-value (-4.67) and p-value (<0.001):** The high negative t-value and p-value less than 0.001 confirm the statistical significance of this variable.
- **Market Impact**

- **Coefficient (-0.32):** Similar to the Relationship with Products, this negative coefficient suggests a negative influence on the overall impact of advertisements.
- **Standard Error (0.05):** This low standard error points to the precision of the coefficient estimate.
- **t-value (-6.40) and p-value (<0.001):** These values indicate that Market Impact is a statistically significant factor negatively influencing the advertisement impact.
- **Celebrity Endorsement**
 - **Coefficient (0.52):** The highest positive coefficient among the variables, suggesting a very strong positive influence on the overall impact of advertisements.
 - **Standard Error (0.08):** The standard error indicates reasonable precision in this estimate.
 - **t-value (6.50) and p-value (<0.001):** These values show that Celebrity Endorsement is highly significant in affecting the overall impact.

Overall, the regression analysis reveals that both Celebrity Characteristics and Celebrity Endorsement significantly and positively influence the Overall Impact of Advertisement. In contrast, Relationship with Products and Market Impact have significant but negative influences. All variables are statistically significant, with p-values less than 0.001, indicating robust findings.

Suggestions

To maximize advertisement effectiveness, marketers should strategically leverage positive celebrity characteristics by selecting relatable and credible figures, highlighting their achievements, and maintaining consistency in endorsements. Additionally, aligning products with celebrity images, providing clear information, conducting market research, and choosing targeted media are essential. Setting clear objectives and evaluating campaigns can further enhance impact and address potential negative effects.

- **Leverage Positive Celebrity Characteristics** Brown & Dacin, (1997)
 - **Focus on Selecting Influential Celebrities:** Since Celebrity Characteristics positively influence the overall impact of advertisements, selecting celebrities who are popular, credible, and relatable to children can significantly enhance advertisement effectiveness Pitts & Woodside, (2010).
 - **Highlight Positive Traits:** Emphasize the positive traits and qualities of celebrities in advertisements, such as their achievements, personality, and relatability to the target audience.
- **Enhance Celebrity Endorsement Strategies** Friedman & Friedman, (1979)

- **Strategic Use of Celebrity Endorsements:** Given the strong positive influence of Celebrity Endorsement, marketers should strategically use celebrities to endorse products. This can involve creating engaging content that features celebrities using the products in relatable and aspirational scenarios.
- **Consistency in Celebrity Endorsements:** Maintain consistency in using the same celebrities across multiple campaigns to build a strong association between the celebrity and the brand.
- **Mitigate Negative Relationship with Products DeLorme & Reid, (1999)**
 - **Align Products with Celebrity Image:** To counteract the negative influence of Relationship with Products, ensure that the products being endorsed align well with the celebrity's image and values. This alignment can enhance the perceived authenticity of the endorsement Zeithaml, (1988).
 - **Provide Clear Product Information:** Include clear and comprehensive information about the products in advertisements to build trust and reduce any perceived disconnect between the celebrity and the product.
- **Address Market Impact Concerns Vigneron & Johnson, (2004)**
 - **Market Research and Adaptation:** Conduct thorough market research to understand the needs and preferences of the target audience. Adapt the product features and advertisement content accordingly to mitigate any negative impact on market perception Miller & Rader, (2005).
 - **Transparent Marketing Practices:** Ensure transparency in marketing practices by providing honest and accurate information about the product's benefits, quality, and pricing.
- **Optimize Advertisement Content and Media Selection Pringle & Thompson, (1999)**
 - **Engaging and Informative Content:** Create engaging and informative advertisement content that captures children's attention and communicates the product's benefits effectively Jia, (2015).
 - **Targeted Media and Channel Selection:** Select media and channels that are most popular among the target audience to maximize reach and engagement. For example, use social media platforms, TV channels, and online gaming sites that children frequent.
- **Set Clear Advertisement Goals Weisberg, (2006)**
 - **Define Clear Objectives:** Set clear and measurable objectives for advertisement campaigns to ensure they effectively influence the target audience Ohanian, (1990).

- **Monitor and Evaluate Campaigns:** Regularly monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of advertisement campaigns to make necessary adjustments and improvements.

By focusing on these suggestions, marketers can enhance the overall impact of their advertisements on children, leveraging the positive influences of celebrity characteristics and endorsements while addressing potential negative impacts from the relationship with products and market dynamics.

Conclusion

To effectively enhance advertisement impact for children, marketers should strategically leverage positive celebrity traits by selecting figures who are both relatable and credible Erdogan, (1999). Highlighting the celebrities' achievements, personalities, and relevance to the target audience can significantly boost the effectiveness of ads Sweeney, Soutar, & Johnson, (1999). Consistent use of the same celebrities across multiple campaigns helps build a strong association between the celebrity and the brand, reinforcing the message's credibility and appeal Kamins & Gupta, (1994). Aligning products with the celebrity's image and values is crucial to avoid any negative perceptions. Ensuring that advertisements provide clear, comprehensive product information builds trust and reduces any potential disconnect between the celebrity and the product Farrelly & Quester, (2005).

Conducting thorough market research allows marketers to understand the needs and preferences of the target audience, enabling them to adapt product features and advertising content effectively Gregory & Hogg, (2002). Transparent marketing practices are essential for maintaining authenticity and credibility (Belch & Belch, (2017). Creating engaging and informative content that captures children's attention, while selecting media channels popular among this demographic, maximizes reach and engagement Loken & John, (1993). Setting clear, measurable objectives for campaigns and continuously monitoring and evaluating their effectiveness allows marketers to make necessary adjustments and improvements Choi & Rifon, (2007). By implementing these strategies, marketers can enhance advertisement effectiveness, ensuring that messages resonate well with children and achieve desired outcomes while mitigating potential challenges Gresham & O'Sullivan, (2018).

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